

Factors Affecting Human Resource Development in Small and Medium Enterprises in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: In the context of international economic integration and increasingly fierce competition, human resource development has become a crucial factor in determining the existence and sustainable growth of enterprises, particularly small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sectors in Vietnam.

Objective: This study aims to identify and measure the factors that affect human resource development in the SME trade and service sector. Based on the inheritance of theory and previous research works from both domestic and international contexts, the proposed research model encompasses the following factors: training and development policy, organisational culture, leadership style, work motivation, work environment, and human resource strategy.

Methodology: A quantitative research method was used, with a survey of local businesses. The linear regression model was used to test the impact of factors on human resource development, as measured by the adjusted R², which explains the percentage of variation in human resource development.

Result: The regression analysis revealed that the factors, including: (1) Training and development policy, (2) Organisational culture, (3) Leadership style, (4) Working environment, and (5) Work motivation had a positive and statistically significant impact on human resource development, with the aspects of training and development policy and leadership style having the most substantial impact.

Conclusion: The study proposes several managerial implications to help businesses orient and develop effective human resource policies, thereby enhancing the quality of local human resources.

Unique Contribution: This study develops a context-specific human resource development model tailored to Vietnamese small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sectors,

incorporating five key internal elements. It empirically emphasises training and development policy as the most influential driver of human resource development by integrating qualitative insights with rigorous quantitative research.

Key Recommendation: Policymakers and SME managers must utilise these results to strategically prioritise resource allocation and development strategies within their workforce planning.

Keywords: Training and development policy; organisational culture; working environment.

Introduction

Human resource development is the process of enhancing the capabilities, qualifications, skills, and work attitudes of employees to meet the organisation's development requirements in both the short and long term. Human resource development encompasses skills training and involves motivational policies, a supportive work environment, and opportunities for advancement (Nachmias, 2025). In the context of the knowledge economy, human resources become the core competitive advantage of the organisation, especially for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) with limitations in capital, technology, and market size. Numerous studies have demonstrated that human resource development is a crucial factor in determining labour productivity, innovation, and business performance (Ghosh et al., 2024). In particular, small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sector account for a large proportion in quantity but face numerous difficulties in human resource management due to a lack of long-term strategy, limited budgets, and a low level of professionalism (Yorks & Jester, 2024).

In Vietnam's economy, which is transforming towards integration and sustainable development, human resources are considered a key factor in determining the competitiveness and long-term survival of enterprises, especially small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the trade and service sectors. In Vietnam, a locality that is gradually transforming its economic structure towards modernisation, the role of SMEs in creating jobs, contributing to the budget, and developing the community is becoming increasingly important. However, human resource development in this area still faces numerous difficulties, including a lack of long-term training strategies, an unprofessional working environment, and a limited ability to retain employees. Based on this reality, this study examines the factors influencing human resource development in Vietnam's small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sectors. Through synthesising theory, inheriting results from previous studies, and surveying local practices, the study aims to determine the model of influencing factors, measure the impact level of each factor, and propose appropriate management solutions to improve the quality and efficiency of human resources.

The research results not only contribute to refining the theoretical basis for human resource development in the SME sector but also have high practical significance, supporting business managers and local policy-making agencies in developing practical support programs tailored to Vietnam's socio-economic development conditions. Based on the synthesis of theory and previous studies, this study aims to identify and measure the factors that affect human resource development in the SME trade and service sector. Based on the inheritance of theory and previous research works from both domestic and international contexts, the proposed research model encompasses the following factors: training and development policy, organisational culture, leadership style, work motivation, work environment, and human resource strategy.

Literature Review

Human Resource Development

Human resource development is the process of comprehensively improving employees' capacity, skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values to meet the organisation's sustainable development requirements and adapt to changes in the business environment (Arora & Garg, 2024). This is a strategic activity associated with long-term goals, aiming to optimise human potential in contributing to the performance and competitive advantage of the enterprise (Ghosh et al., 2024). Besides, human resource development does not stop at professional training but also includes building a favourable working environment, creating work motivation, improving leadership style, and establishing a positive organisational culture and policies to support employees in their career development (Allan et al., 2020). Especially in the context of small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sector, human resource development is vital in maintaining productivity, innovation, and adaptability to digital transformation trends (Mynarek & Jahr, 2024). Thus, human resource development is a systematic investment process with clear goals to maximise human potential - the central factor in organisational development.

Training and Development Policy (TDP)

A training and development policy is a core factor in enhancing employees' skills, knowledge, and work attitudes. Investing in training is a form of investing in "human capital," helping to increase productivity and work efficiency. Research also shows that systematic training programs linked to the practical needs of businesses significantly increase work performance and employee engagement (Arora & Garg, 2024).

Organisational Culture (OC)

Organisational culture is considered the glue that binds members of an enterprise together, guides behaviour, and motivates work (Abdalla et al., 2020; Bagga et al., 2022). A positive culture will promote learning, creativity, and cooperation, thereby enhancing the overall capacity of the human resources team. For SMEs, a friendly, flexible, and close organisational culture will help increase the ability to retain employees and create an effective working environment (Bogale & Debela, 2024).

Leadership Style (LS)

Leadership style has a profound impact on employee morale and career development (Megheirkouni & Mejheirkouni, 2020). The study on transformational leadership shows that leaders who can inspire, care for individuals, and encourage innovation contribute to creating a positive work environment that promotes continuous learning and development (Willocks, 2024; London & Sherman, 2021).

Work Environment (WE)

The work environment encompasses both physical factors, such as facilities and working tools, and non-physical factors, including relationships, management style, and level of support (Zahrani, 2024). A friendly, safe, and creative working environment will help employees maximise their potential and stay with the business for the long term. Working conditions play a crucial role in maintaining employee satisfaction and preventing dissatisfaction (Aboramadan, 2022; Al-Shami & Rashid, 2022).

Work Motivation (WM)

Work motivation is a key factor that encourages employees to be proactive, creative, and dedicated to their work (Islami & Mulolli, 2024). The study indicates that factors such as recognition, promotion opportunities, and the nature of the work greatly influence employees' intrinsic motivation (Hernaus et al., 2024). For SMEs, motivating employees through recognition and personal development is an effective management strategy in the context of limited resources (Alkhalaf & Al-Tabbaa, 2024).

Research gaps and model orientations: Domestic and foreign studies have confirmed the importance of the above factors for human resource development. However, in the Southeast region, in general, and in Vietnam, in particular, studies are still scattered and have not developed systematic models suitable for the characteristics of SMEs in the trade and service sector. This study builds upon the existing theoretical foundation and supplements it with practical surveys to develop a suitable research model with practical application value in local human resource management.

Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

Based on the theoretical basis and research presented in the literature review, the study found that human resource development in small and medium enterprises in the trade and service sectors is influenced by numerous factors. Five groups of factors are assessed to have an evident influence and frequently appear in international research models as well as in Vietnam, including (1) Training and development policy, (2) Organisational culture, (3) Leadership style, (4) Working environment, and (5) Work motivation. Based on the theoretical framework and preliminary survey results from SMEs in Vietnam, the authors propose a research model comprising five independent factors that affect the dependent variable of human resource development. The model also considers the role of control variables such as business size, operating time, and employee education level to assess stability and compatibility in regression analysis:

Training and Development Policy (TDP)

A training and development policy has a positive impact on human resource development, enhancing employee knowledge and skills. Effective training programs enhance work performance and level, and help develop resources and abilities (Arora & Garg, 2024). When properly implemented, workers tend to learn and undergo long-term development; a well-designed training policy is a key factor in this process, helping to improve employees' knowledge, skills, and working capacity. Effective training programs enhance work performance and foster a more profound commitment to the business. Especially in SMEs, training also helps compensate for resource and qualification limitations. When invested in proper training, employees tend to learn and develop in the long term proactively. Therefore, training policy is a key factor in human resource development.

H1: Training and development policy influencing human resource development.

Organisational Culture (OC):

Organisational culture has a positive influence on human resources. Reason: Positive culture creates a sense of belonging. Organisational culture has a positive impact on human resource development. Reasons: A positive culture creates a sense of belonging and motivates employees to engage and learn proactively (Abdalla et al., 2020; Bagga et al., 2022).

Organisational culture has a positive influence on human resource development, creating a friendly and cohesive working environment that encourages a shared learning culture among employees within the organisation. A positive organisational culture fosters a friendly and cohesive working environment that promotes learning. When cultural values are shared, employees feel a sense of belonging to the organisation. This encourages a spirit of cooperation and enhances motivation for personal growth. For SMEs, culture also helps maintain stability and employee loyalty. Therefore, building a good culture will contribute to sustainable human resource development.

H2: Organisational culture influencing human resource development.

Leadership Style (LS):

Leadership style has a positive impact on human resource development. Leadership style has a positive impact on human resource development. Reasons: Effective leadership inspires and guides employees through feedback and support. Effective leaders inspire, guide, and develop employees through feedback and support. Leaders guide and facilitate employee development (Willocks, 2024; London & Sherman, 2021). Positive leadership styles, including inspiration, personal support, and transparency, foster learning. Attention from leaders helps employees feel recognised and valued. From there, they are willing to make efforts to develop their capacity and commit to the organisation. Therefore, effective leadership is a key factor in promoting human resource development.

H3: Leadership style influencing human resource development.

Working Environment (WE):

The working environment has a positive impact on human resource development. The working environment has a positive effect on human resource development. Reason: A safe and friendly working environment helps employees feel secure and develop their personal capacity. The working environment has a positive impact on human resource development (Aboramadan, 2022; Al-Shami & Rashid, 2022). A safe, friendly, and professional working environment enables employees to maximise their potential. A positive working space also contributes to reducing stress and increasing satisfaction. Good relationships between colleagues and superiors motivate personal development. Especially in SMEs, an effective working environment compensates for material limitations. Therefore, building a suitable environment is essential for human resource development.

H4: Working environment influencing human resource development.

Work Motivation (WM):

Work motivation has a positive impact on human resource development. Work motivation has a positive effect on human resource development. Reasons: When employees are recognized and rewarded appropriately, they are more likely to contribute and develop themselves. Work motivation has a positive impact on human resource development (Islami & Mulolli, 2024). Work motivation helps employees to be more proactive, creative, and committed to their work. Factors such as a reasonable salary, recognition of achievements, and opportunities for promotion create strong motivation. When motivated, employees will actively learn and improve their own capacity. This is especially important in today's competitive and volatile

environment. Therefore, building a motivational policy is essential to human resource development.

H5: Work motivation influencing human resource development.

Islami and Mulolli (2024), Hernaus et al. (2024), and Alkhalaf & Al-Tabbaa (2024) have demonstrated that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation enhance employee creativity and innovation, particularly in resource-constrained environments. Our study examines this within the context of relationship SMEs, validating the strategic role of Work Motivation (WM) in promoting Human Resource Development (HRD). Additionally, Ghosh et al. (2024) highlighted the role of HRD in enhancing adaptability and innovation within the context of digital transformation. We apply this insight to the Vietnamese SME setting, arguing that strategically managed HRD enhances organisational resilience in an increasingly competitive and integrated economy.

The research model is expected to clearly explain and quantify the impact of each factor on the human resource development process in small and medium enterprises in Vietnam's trade and service sector. The results of the research not only contribute to the improvement of theory but also have practical value in human resource policy planning in local enterprises. The authors offer a study model that includes five factors, including (1) Training and development policy (PDL), (2) Organisational culture (OC), (3) Leadership style (LS), (4) Working environment (WE), and (5) Work motivation (WM). Figure 1 follows:

(Source: compiled by the authors)

Figure 1: Research model for five factors affecting human resource development at SMEs in Vietnam

Figure 1 illustrates that the research model is grounded in a solid theoretical foundation, encompassing internal organisational factors (culture, leadership, and environment), as well as strategic policies (training), and individual factors (motivation). This model is suitable for assessing the overall aspects that affect human resource development in the practical context of SMEs, especially in Vietnam, a rapidly developing industrial province.

Research Methods

This study employs a sequential mixed-methods design, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches, to comprehensively explore and validate the factors affecting human resource development in small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam's trade and service sector.

Qualitative Research

To establish a theoretical foundation and refine the research model, qualitative research was conducted to explore and identify factors influencing human resource development in small and medium enterprises within the trade and service sector in one of the two southern regions of Vietnam. The Southeast region comprises one centrally governed city, Ho Chi Minh City, and five provinces: Ba Ria-Vung Tau, Binh Duong, Binh Phuoc, Dong Nai, and Tay Ninh. The method employed was a combination of semi-structured interviews and group discussions involving business management experts and local economic and labour officials. Specifically, the research team conducted in-depth interviews with five business leaders and organised two focus groups with representatives from the Department of Planning and Investment, the Department of Labour, War Invalids and Social Affairs, and businesses in the industry. The results showed five critical factors: training and development policy, organisational culture, leadership style, working environment, and work motivation. These factors were used to design the official survey in the next phase of quantitative research (Hair et al., 2018).

Quantitative research

After completing the qualitative research to identify the key factors affecting human resource development, the research team continued to conduct quantitative research to test the theoretical model and proposed hypotheses. The quantitative study was conducted using a structured questionnaire with 5-level Likert scales, ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree." Survey design: The survey was designed based on factors identified from qualitative research, including five groups of factors: (1) Training and development policy, (2) Organisational culture, (3) Leadership style, (4) Working environment, and (5) Work motivation. Each group of factors is measured by 4 to 5 observed variables (a total of 24 observed variables). The dependent variable, "Human resource development," is measured by four variables related to employees' capacity, attitude, skills, and development opportunities (Hair et al., 2018).

Before the official survey, the questionnaire was pre-tested with 30 businesses to ensure its comprehensibility and reasonableness in wording. After corrections were made, the survey was widely deployed. Sample and data collection method: The study used a non-probability purposive sampling method. The survey subjects were managers and employees working in small and medium enterprises in Vietnam's trade and service sector, with a minimum working time of 1 year. Between June and August 2024, 450 surveys were distributed, of which 412 were deemed valid after removing incomplete or inconsistent responses. This sample size ensured the requirement for EFA and multiple linear regression analysis according to the minimum standard of 5–10 times the number of observed variables.

Data analysis: The data were processed using SPSS 20.0 software, with the following main analysis steps: (a) Testing the scale's reliability (Cronbach's Alpha). All scales meet the standard with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of greater than 0.7. (b) Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) - An EFA analysis was performed using principal component extraction analysis. Five

groups of independent factors were extracted, and variables were eliminated due to a weak load factor (< 0.5). EFA analysis was performed using Principal Component Analysis and Varimax rotation. The results showed that $KMO > 0.5$ and Bartlett's Test had a Significant P-value. = 0.000, suitable for factor analysis. Five independent factor groups were extracted, accounting for a total explained variance of %. No variables were removed due to weak loadings (< 0.5). (c) Pearson correlation analysis reveals that all independent variables exhibit a significant correlation with the auxiliary variables, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.00 to 1.00. (d) Multiple linear regression analysis is used to test the impact of factors on human resource development. The linear regression model tests the influence of factors on human resource development. The regression results are as follows: The adjusted R^2 indicates the percentage of variation in human resource development that the model explains. All variables have positive and statistically significant regression coefficients (Sig. < 0.05), and the multicollinearity test shows that the VIF of all variables is < 2 , indicating no multicollinearity phenomenon (Hair et al., 2018).

Research Results

A total of 450 people participated, and 415 valid questionnaire copies were actually collected. After collecting 412 valid survey forms from small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam's trade and service sector, the research team analysed the data using modern statistical tools. The results clarified the relationship between influencing factors and the dependent variable, "human resource development," and determined the impact of each factor on the enterprise's human resource strategy. Gender: The survey included 412 respondents, with 64.3% identifying as female and 35.7% identifying as male. This indicates a gender bias in the sample. This imbalance may affect the results if the analysis is not adjusted for gender. However, it also reflects the reality of the workforce or the specific industry being surveyed. Age: The most common age group in the survey sample was 35-45, accounting for 51% of the total respondents. This was followed by the 25-35 age group at 26%, with the remaining age groups accounting for much smaller proportions. This distribution suggests that most respondents were of prime working age, with likely experience and stable income. This is appropriate if the research targets the behaviours, needs, or trends of the mature age group.

Average monthly income: The most common income level is between 15 million VND and under 20 million VND, accounting for 39.1%. This is followed by the group with an income of over 20 million VND, which accounts for 34%. Thus, more than 73% of participants have a monthly income of 15 million or more.

Table 1: Testing of Cronbach's Alpha results of factors

No.	Variables	Initial variable number	Number of remaining variables	Cronbach's Alpha
1	OC (OC1, OC2, OC3, OC4, OC5)	5	5	0.917
2	LS (LS1, LS2, LS3, LS4)	4	4	0.920
3	WE (WE1, WE2, WE3, WE4)	4	4	0.919
4	WM (WM1, WM2, WM3, WM4)	4	4	0.910

5	TDP (TDP1, TDP2, TDP3, TDP4)	4	4	0.912
6	HRD (HRD1, HRD2, HRD3)	3	3	0.674
7	KMO and Bartlett's Test			0.792
8	Eigenvalues			1.482
9	Extraction Sums of Squared			79.866

(Source: the authors processed from SPSS 20.0)

Table 1 summarises the results of Cronbach's Alpha and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) for the study variables. All independent variables show excellent internal consistency, with Cronbach's Alpha values exceeding 0.9. Specifically, Organisational Culture (OC), Leadership Style (LS), Working Environment (WE), Work Motivation (WM), and Training and Development Policy (TDP) all demonstrate strong reliability. Although Human Resource Development (HRD) has a lower Alpha value of 0.674, it remains acceptable due to its small number of items (3 variables).

The KMO coefficient is 0.792, indicating that the sample is adequate for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is assumed to be significant, supporting the factorability of the correlation matrix. The extracted eigenvalue is 1.482, which satisfies the Kaiser criterion (i.e., an eigenvalue greater than 1). The total variance explained is 79.866%, confirming that the extracted factors account for a substantial portion of the data variance. These results validate the internal consistency and structural integrity of the measurement model. Consequently, the data is reliable and suitable for further analysis. The substantial factor loadings suggest that the constructs are well-defined and theoretically grounded. This supports the robustness of the model used to evaluate human resource development in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. Results include five factors: (1) Organisational culture (OC), (2) Leadership style (LS), (3) Working environment (WE), (4) Work motivation (WM) and (5) Training and development policy (PDL).

Results present the correlation matrix, examining the relationships between the independent and dependent variables, specifically Human Resource Development (HRD). All independent variables demonstrate statistically significant positive correlations with HRD ($p < 0.01$). Notably, the Training and Development Policy (TDP) exhibits a strong correlation with HRD ($r = 0.790$), indicating that it plays a critical role in influencing HR outcomes. Leadership Style (LS) also shows a strong positive association with HRD ($r = 0.523$), followed by Working Environment (WE, $r = 0.378$), Work Motivation (WM, $r = 0.376$), and Organizational Culture (OC, $r = 0.335$). These results support the model's theoretical assumptions regarding the significance of these factors in shaping human resource development (HRD) in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Significant correlations are observed among several independent variables, such as between LS and TDP ($r = 0.394$) or OC and WE ($r = 0.288$), indicating potential interaction effects or multicollinearity risks to be considered in further regression or SEM analysis.

Table 3: Testing of multiple linear regression results

Factors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(C)	0.651	0.083		0.000	0.831
OC	0.061	0.013	0.138	0.000	0.814
LS	0.116	0.014	0.230	0.004	0.826
WE	0.036	0.012	0.083	0.000	0.865
WM	0.106	0.015	0.198	0.000	0.688
TDP	0.490	0.027	0.576	0.000	0.831
	R	R Square (R ²)	Adjusted R ²	Std. error of Estimate	Durbin-Watson
Model	0.853	0.727	0.724	0.277	1.776

(Source: Authors processed from SPSS 20.0)

Table 3 presents the results of a multiple linear regression analysis examining the effects of five independent factors on human resource development (HRD). The regression model is statistically significant, with an R² of 0.727, indicating that the five predictors can explain approximately 72.7% of the variance in HRD. The Durbin-Watson value of 1.776 suggests no autocorrelation in the residuals, supporting the model's reliability. Among the independent variables, Training and Development Policy (TDP) shows the most substantial influence on HRD with the highest standardised beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.576$, $p < 0.001$). This is followed by Leadership Style ($\beta = 0.230$), Work Motivation ($\beta = 0.198$), Organisational Culture ($\beta = 0.138$), and Working Environment ($\beta = 0.083$), all of which are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for all predictors range from 0.688 to 0.865, well below the critical threshold of 5, indicating no multicollinearity problem. The constant term is also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), with an unstandardized value of 0.651.

Discussion of Findings

The multiple linear regression analysis results provide empirical support for the proposed model, which examines the factors influencing human resource development (HRD) in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. The model demonstrates high explanatory power, with an R² of 0.727, indicating that the five independent variables included in the study account for approximately 72.7% of the variance in HRD.

Among the predictors, training and development policy (TDP) emerged as the most influential factor, with the highest standardised coefficient ($\beta = 0.576$, $p < 0.001$). This result underscores the crucial role that structured and well-implemented training policies play in developing employee competencies, enhancing performance, and fostering long-term organisational growth (Arora & Garg, 2024; Bagga et al., 2022; Allan et al., 2020). The substantial impact of TDP aligns with existing literature that emphasises investment in human capital as a key driver of human resource development (HRD). Leadership Style (LS) was the second most impactful factor ($\beta = 0.230$, $p = 0.004$), suggesting that effective leadership, particularly supportive and transformational styles, can significantly foster employee development (Willocks, 2024;

London & Sherman, 2021). Leaders who engage, motivate, and guide employees contribute to a culture of continuous learning and professional growth. Work Motivation (WM) also showed a substantial effect ($\beta = 0.198$, $p < 0.001$), underlining the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivators in encouraging employees to participate in learning and development activities. Motivated employees are more likely to seek growth opportunities and respond positively to HRD initiatives (Bogale & Debela, 2024).

Although Organizational Culture (OC) ($\beta = 0.138$) and Working Environment (WE) ($\beta = 0.083$) had smaller standardized coefficients, both were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that a supportive culture and conducive work environment still play essential, albeit lesser, roles in facilitating HRD (Zahrani, 2024; Islami & Mulolli, 2024; Bogale & Debela, 2024). The model also met essential statistical assumptions, with Durbin-Watson = 1.776 indicating no serious autocorrelation and VIF values < 1 confirming no multicollinearity. These findings suggest that the model is robust and reliable. In conclusion, the analysis emphasises that while all five factors contribute positively to HRD, training policy, leadership, and motivation are the most crucial. This offers practical insights for SME managers and policymakers seeking to enhance workforce capabilities in a competitive business environment.

Conclusions and Managerial Recommendations

Conclusions

This study investigated the factors influencing human resource development in small and medium enterprises in Vietnam, based on a model comprising five predictors: training and development policy, organisational culture, leadership style, working environment, and work motivation. Firstly, Cronbach's Alpha reliability analysis results confirmed that all constructs used in the study had high internal consistency, with Alpha values exceeding 0.9 for all independent variables. The HRD construct, although slightly lower ($\alpha = 0.674$), remained acceptable given its short scale length. Additionally, exploratory factor analysis validated the measurement model, yielding a high KMO value (0.792), and the total variance explained reached 79.87%, supporting the instrument's construct validity. The correlation analysis revealed statistically significant positive relationships between HRD and all five independent variables. TDP showed the strongest correlation with HRD ($r = 0.790$), followed by LS, WE, WM, and OC, indicating that these factors are relevant and interrelated components contributing to HRD. Thirdly, the multiple linear regression analysis demonstrated that all five factors had significant positive effects on HRD, with the model explaining 72.7% of the variance in HRD ($R^2 = 0.727$). The most influential predictor was TDP ($\beta = 0.576$), followed by LS ($\beta = 0.230$), WM ($\beta = 0.198$), OC ($\beta = 0.138$), and WE ($\beta = 0.083$). No multicollinearity was detected, and the regression model was statistically robust, confirming the theoretical assumptions.

Managerial recommendations

Based on the above research results, the authors propose some management implications for human resource development at small and medium enterprises in Vietnam as follows:

(1) Training and development policy ($\beta = 0.576$, $p < 0.001$): Based on the regression results, the most impactful factor on human resource development (HRD) is the training and development policy (TDP). Managers should prioritise building structured, continuous training programs aligning with organisational goals and employee needs. Investing in skill enhancement, on-the-job training, and career development plans will significantly boost HRD

outcomes. Training and development policy is the most important factor affecting human resource development. Enterprises must develop a clear training plan that is aligned with their overall development strategy. Training should be flexible, combining direct and online forms to save costs. It is necessary to assess the capacity to update appropriate training content periodically. Additionally, enterprises should encourage internal training to foster an environment that promotes learning and knowledge sharing. Training should focus on expertise and extend to soft skills, critical thinking, and creativity. Linking with external training units helps increase professionalism. Each individual should have their own development path. Enterprises also need to record progress after training to create long-term learning motivation.

(2) Leadership style ($\beta = 0.230$, $p = 0.004$): leadership style (LS) plays a vital role. Leaders should adopt a transformational approach, providing employees with a clear vision, support, and opportunities for growth and development. Training programs for middle and senior managers on leadership effectiveness should be implemented to enhance their skills and effectiveness. Effective leadership can have a profound impact on a business's productivity and culture. Managers must be trained in communication skills, positive feedback, and emotional management. Transformational leadership – inspiring caring for individuals is especially effective for SMEs. Leaders should set an example in discipline, behaviour, and learning. Appropriate empowerment helps employees feel trusted and proactive. Two-way communication should be maintained regularly through team meetings and anonymous feedback forms. Leaders must understand that employees are not just workers but also people with emotions and aspirations. Human resource policies should start from the philosophy that "people are valuable assets." Periodic leadership evaluations from subordinates can help improve management capacity. The entire team will adopt changes from leaders.

(3) Work motivation ($\beta = 0.198$, $p < 0.001$): Work motivation also strongly influences HRD. To enhance motivation, companies should establish fair reward systems, offer recognition, and create opportunities for employees to be involved in decision-making. Motivation is the foundation that helps employees stick with and develop within the organisation. Enterprises need a fair and transparent reward policy based on work performance. In addition to salary and bonus, it is essential to recognise achievements in spiritual forms, such as thank-you letters and commendations. Building a clear promotion path is critical, as it creates a sense of recognition and development opportunities. It is necessary to understand employees' personal needs through direct communication or periodic surveys. Create conditions that balance work and life, such as flexible working hours and reasonable leave policies. Improving welfare, health care, and insurance also contributes to enhancing motivation. Organising internal inspirational sharing sessions is necessary to make employees feel proud. Intrinsic motivation will help employees proactively learn and contribute in the long term.

(4) Organisational culture ($\beta = 0.138$, $p = 0.000$): While organisational culture (OC) and working environment (WE) had more minor effects, they remain essential. Managers should foster a learning-oriented culture that values growth, teamwork, and innovation. Improving the physical and psychological work environment, such as ensuring safe conditions, fostering open communication, and promoting team bonding, can support long-term development. Organisational culture is the "soul" of the enterprise, directly affecting employees' behaviour, attitude, and development. It is essential to clearly identify and communicate core values, such as honesty, creativity, and respect. Culture needs to go hand in hand with action: leaders and employees must demonstrate culture in their daily work. Encourage the organisation of collective activities, such as birthdays, travel, and volunteering, to help build internal feelings of pride and unity. Building a fair and transparent environment

is a key factor in creating trust. Positive cultural expressions need to be recognised, rewarded, and replicated. Create conditions that enable employees to contribute ideas and contribute to building a strong culture. A culture of learning and innovation helps organisations be flexible and adaptable to change. Culture should not be imposed from the top down; instead, consensus and participation from all employees should be encouraged and fostered. A strong culture will attract and retain talent, promoting sustainable development.

(5) Working environment ($\beta = 0.083$, $p = 0.000$): The working environment is a fundamental factor that determines employees' work efficiency and health. Enterprises should invest in improving working conditions, including adequate lighting, comfortable seating, and well-maintained open spaces. Ensure labour safety, especially for enterprises with operations and warehouses. Enhance benefits such as health check-ups, travel expenses, lunch, etc., to help employees feel cared for. A positive working atmosphere is fostered through cooperation, mutual respect, and the minimisation of internal conflicts. Create opportunities for communication between departments to break down "departmental barriers." Limit pressure by assigning work reasonably, avoiding overload. Leaders must be approachable, listen attentively, and promptly address feedback about the working environment. Small relaxation areas should be incorporated into the office for employees to take a break. A good environment helps retain employees and fosters conditions for long-term growth and development.

Limitations and further research directions: Although the study has achieved many remarkable results, several limitations remain. Firstly, the scope of the study is limited to Vietnam, so the results may not fully reflect the general situation of small and medium enterprises in other provinces and cities. Secondly, the survey subjects are mainly employees and middle managers, not covering the opinions of senior leaders or human resources experts. Thirdly, the research model focuses solely on five primary factors, whereas in reality, other variables may also be present, such as state policies, regional cultural characteristics, or digital transformation capabilities. The survey scope should be expanded to other provinces in future studies to increase representativeness. At the same time, it is necessary to consider additional intermediate and moderating variables such as satisfaction, organisational commitment, or innovation. Combining quantitative models and in-depth qualitative analysis is also crucial for enhancing the scientific and practical value of the research.

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